

Research Article

1030 nm Dissipative Soliton Mode-Locked Fiber Laser Source via Bi₂Te₃ Side-Polished Fiber Saturable Absorber

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Abstract: In this study, the author presents the experimental performance of a dissipative soliton mode-locked fiber laser utilizing a liquid-phase Bi₂Te₃ topological insulator (TI) as a saturable absorber (SA). The Bi₂Te₃-based SA, synthesized in a solution-processable form, demonstrates nonlinear optical properties, enabling stable passive mode-locking in a ytterbium-doped fiber laser configured in a ring cavity. Our findings underscore the viability of liquid-phase topological insulators as versatile, high-performance saturable absorbers for ultrafast photonics. Furthermore, this work expands the application scope of Bi₂Te₃ beyond conventional solid-state devices, demonstrating its adaptability in fiber laser systems for generating dissipative solitons. The results affirm the potential of TI-based materials in advancing compact, high-energy pulsed laser sources for applications in optical communications, material processing, and nonlinear optics.

Keywords: Dissipative soliton; Fiber Laser; Ytterbium-doped fiber.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, passively mode-locked fiber lasers have gained significant attention due to their compact design, cost-effectiveness, and simplified architecture compared to actively mode-locked systems (Ahmad, Lutfi, Samion, & Zaini, 2024a; Gao et al., 2020). Various passive mode-locking techniques have been explored, including nonlinear loop mirrors (NOLMs) based on nonlinear interferometry and nonlinear polarization rotation (NPR) which is based on Kerr nonlinearity, both enabling compact ultrafast laser systems (Ahmad, Lutfi, Ortaç, et al., 2024; Ahmad, Lutfi, Samion, Zaini, et al., 2024). While semiconductor saturable absorber mirrors (SESAMs) remain a mature technology, their limitations—such as intricate fabrication processes, narrow operational bandwidth, and high costs—have driven the search for alternative saturable absorbers (SAs) (Sui et al., 2023). Carbon-based materials, including single-wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs), graphene, and graphene oxide, have emerged as promising candidates due to their broadband operation and affordability (Duan et al., 2017). However, SWCNTs exhibit wavelength-dependent performance tied to their diameter, and graphene-based SAs, though broadband, face challenges such as high saturation intensities.

Recent advancements have highlighted topological insulators (TIs), such as Bi₂Se₃, Sb₂Te₃, Bi₂Te₃, as novel SAs with good nonlinear optical properties. These materials exhibit metallic surface states and insulating bulk states due to their unique bandgap structures. For instance, Bi₂Se₃ possesses

a topological energy gap of $\sim 0.2\text{--}0.3$ eV, enabling saturable absorption at wavelengths below $4.1\ \mu\text{m}$ (0.3 eV) (Peiguang Yan et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2018). TIs offer advantages such as ultralow saturation intensity, broad operational bandwidth, and cost-effective fabrication (Ahmad, Lutfi, et al., 2025). In this work, we present the demonstration of an all-fiber, Yb-doped mode-locked laser operating at $1\ \mu\text{m}$ using a Bi_2Te_3 SA. The laser employs an all-normal dispersion cavity, with Bi_2Te_3 directly deposited onto a side-polished fiber. The results validate Bi_2Te_3 as a high-performance SA for ultrafast lasers in the $1\ \mu\text{m}$ regime, combining ease of integration with robust nonlinear response. This study advances the application of TI-based materials in compact, high-efficiency pulsed laser systems, bridging a gap in wavelength-specific dissipative mode-locking research.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

Figure 1 illustrates the design of an all-normal dispersion (ANDi) fiber laser incorporating a saturable absorber (SA) made from Bi_2Te_3 deposited onto a side-polished fiber segment. The ring cavity incorporates a 0.3-meter segment of Yb-1200 gain fiber, featuring a core numerical aperture (NA) of 0.2 and a cutoff wavelength of 1010 ± 70 nm. This ytterbium-doped fiber (YDF) has a core absorption peak of $1200\ \text{dB/m}$ at $976\ \text{nm}$ and a mode field diameter measuring $4.4\ \mu\text{m}$ at $1060\ \text{nm}$. Pumping is provided by a $974\ \text{nm}$ multimode laser diode (LD) coupled into the cavity via a fused wavelength division multiplexer (WDM). Light travels unidirectionally past the YDF due to a polarization-insensitive isolator (PI-ISO). Mode-locking begins when the Bi_2Te_3 -coated side-polished fiber is inserted; a two-paddle polarization controller connected to the fiber allows fine-tuning of the polarization state within the cavity. The laser output exits through a 90:10 optical coupler, which splits the light, directing 10% to measurement equipment and returning 90% back into the WDM to complete the ring.

Figure 1. Laser cavity configuration.

3. FINDINGS

Stable, self-starting mode-locked operation commenced at a pump threshold of 153 mW and remained stable up to 270 mW. At the maximum pump power of 270 mW, the optical spectrum of the generated pulses (Figure 2(a)) is centered at 1030 nm and has a 3-dB spectral width of 9.4 nm. The spectrum shows sharp edges, a signature characteristic of all-normal dispersion (ANDi) fiber lasers as documented in recent studies (Ahmad, Lutfi, Samion, & Zaini, 2024b; Ahmad, M Lutfi, et al., 2025). The temporal output, recorded using an oscilloscope and presented in Figure 2(b), reveals a pulse train with a repetition rate of 26.4 MHz, corresponding to a consistent pulse separation of 37.8 ns.

Figure 2. Mode-locked laser (a) optical spectrum, (b) oscilloscope trace

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we have successfully demonstrated a dissipative soliton mode-locked ytterbium-doped fiber laser using a liquid-phase Bi_2Te_3 topological insulator as a saturable absorber. The solution-processed Bi_2Te_3 exhibited a strong nonlinear optical response, enabling stable mode-locking within a ring cavity configuration. These results validate the effectiveness of liquid-phase topological insulators as practical and efficient saturable absorbers for ultrafast laser applications. Moreover, this work highlights the potential of Bi_2Te_3 to extend beyond its conventional solid-state usage, offering a flexible platform for the development of compact, high-energy ultrafast photonic systems. The demonstrated approach opens promising avenues for integrating TI-based materials into next-generation fiber lasers aimed at applications in optical communication, precision materials processing, and nonlinear photonics.

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